

Inclusive partnerships for forecasting and managing HAB risk in Washington State coastal communities

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Abstract

Current health and climate crises will require a proactive approach, focused on establishing and fostering partnerships to identify and eliminate primary causes of the disconnect between humans and nature. In the northeast Pacific Ocean and the adjacent coastal areas, lessons focused on human respect for nature have been learned through unique scientific partnerships that blend current-day technology with observational knowledge of Indigenous communities, such as the study of harmful algal blooms (HABs). Explicit examples of proactive strategies used to address environmental problems include projects focused on understanding and mitigating HAB impacts in coastal Washington State. These projects are based upon mutual respect of Indigenous and non-Indigenous scientists and include: 1) establishment of the Olympic Region Harmful Algal Bloom (ORHAB) partnership, 2) sharing of science knowledge in tribal youth camps; 3) development of a forecasting system for HABs to alert resource managers of the risk they pose to shellfish harvests and community health. These collaborative projects teach all participants the value of reciprocity, demonstrating how the bounty of the ocean and its protection can promote our well-being. Programs that give equal respect to all voices promote proactive strategies that foster both human and ocean health.

Keywords: HAB, climate change, Indigenous partnerships, sato-umi, health, Washington State

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Introduction

The growing movement calling for *reciprocal* healing of nature and people (Kimmerer, 2015; Hayden, 2019; Fleischner and Sewall, 2020; Varanasi, 2020; Myers and Frumkin, 2021) considers Indigenous knowledge about conservation and resource management with increasing regard (Kimmerer, 2015; Polfus *et al.* 2016; Ban *et al.*, 2018; Atlas *et al.*, 2020), especially realizing that Indigenous people effectively manage over 40% of the world's ecosystems (Garnett *et al.*, 2018). Given that biodiversity is among the highest on lands managed by Indigenous communities, the protection of these lands and respect for the voices of their inhabitants are critical in the survival of the entire human species (Schuster *et al.*, 2019). Indigenous traditional ecological knowledge has recently been recognized to be a critical component of decision-making, contributing to scientific, technical, social, and economic advancements of the United States and to our collective understanding of the natural world (Memorandum, 2021). By bringing together experts of all backgrounds, Indigenous and non-Indigenous scientists alike, solutions are created that promote the harmonious co-existence of people and nature.

The linkage of human and ocean health

Humans are an integral part of the natural world who often take advantage of the healing properties of nature –by walking on the seashore or hiking in the forest. But it is time to shift the focus from nature *for* health to nature *and* health, allowing human and ecological health to be joint goals (Varanasi, 2020; Varanasi *et al.*, 2021). In fact, the Japanese term “Sato-umi”, meaning village-seas, was created to describe the dependency

of human and nature interactions to achieve productive and diverse ocean ecosystems (Makino, 2011). This centuries-old goal of living harmoniously with nature is shared by Indigenous communities in many parts of the world.

Community based partnerships

The Sato-umi principles (Table 1) have provided lessons for collaborative studies of HABs that have passed the test of time – and that are still ongoing today in Washington State, USA. The

Table 1. The Sato-umi principles

- Share knowledge, including local knowledge

- Listen

- Foster collaborative and equitable relationships from the inception of an idea

- Conduct science as a collective action

- Cultivate mutual respect

Olympic Region HAB ([ORHAB](#)) partnership was established in response to a coastal survey that highlighted HABs as the largest coastal issue. This grassroots idea came from the communities to scientists, not the other way around, and has lasted the test of time as a partnership of Indigenous scientists, managers, and community members with State and Federal scientists (Fig. 1). ORHAB empowers tribal and state managers to make scientifically-based decisions about managing and mitigating HAB impacts on coastal fishery resources. ORHAB is the only HAB project of its kind that has been transferred from federal to state and tribal government

support, funded by tribal governments and a tax paid by recreational shellfish harvesters when they purchase a state shellfishing license (Trainer and Suddleson, 2005). Thus, ORHAB is funded and operated by the community that it serves. This community-driven science partnership has formed the basis of successful programs in Puget Sound, WA (the SoundToxins partnership), Oregon, and Alaska (the SEATOR program) as well other parts of the world, including Guatemala and Indonesia (Trick *et al.*, 2012; Trainer *et al.*, 2016). These partnerships demonstrate that local people are an indispensable part of ecosystem studies (Makino, 2011) and show the critical need to *foster collaborative and equitable relationships from the inception of an idea* – by including the people who live on the coast in the design and implementation of scientific studies.

The success of community-driven programs (such as ORHAB) has been highlighted by Elinor Ostrom, the only woman to receive a Nobel Prize in Economic Sciences. She states in her work that projects established by resource users - by communities, not governments - achieve the greatest sustainability (Ostrom, 1990). Cooperation is maintained by establishment of trust. ORHAB is an example of this established trust in a science partnership. Ostrom's work emphasizes the need to implement community-driven approaches in dealing with global environmental problems, including HABs and climate change.

Our initial meetings with tribal elders were held two decades ago, in which we asked for their ideas to sustain the ORHAB partnership. We spoke about all the great work we wished to do on their coastal beaches and the adjacent

Fig. 1. ORHAB sites on the Washington State, U.S.A. coast for phytoplankton sampling (•), toxin analysis (L), and razor clam harvest (see legend; Trainer and Suddleson, 2005). Partners include NOAA, the Washington State Department of Health (WDOH), the Washington Department of Fish and Wildlife (WDFW), the University of Washington Olympic Natural Resources Center (ONRC), the Quinault Indian Nation (Quinault), the Makah Tribe (Makah), and Quileute Tribe (Quileute). Reprinted from Varanasi *et al.* (2021).

seas by building HAB monitoring programs and establishing labs where tribes could do their own testing. The elders listened but sat silently until we talked about our plans to teach their children. As we *listened* to them, the importance of *conducting our science as a collective action*, by not only working with adults, but by teaching the children, the next generation, was established as a need within their community. The partnership was strengthened by including all voices – children and adults, western and Indigenous scientists. This led to the establishment of a summer camp curriculum that included lectures on HABs, introduction to phytoplankton identification by microscopy, and rapid toxin testing. The summer camp teachers included tribal elders who spoke about bioluminescent waters that

warned of toxic shellfish, demonstrating to the children the value of their traditional knowledge of HABs.

Knowledge sharing

These summer camps were held on the coast of the Pacific Northwest of the USA, first inhabited by Indigenous people with the present-day names, Quinault Indian Nation and Quileute, Hoh, and Makah Tribes. These tribes have taught us respect for the sea by their saying “when the tide is out, the table is set”, referring to the historical abundance of shellfish during low tides. During our first meetings with Makah tribal elders, they spoke about a highly productive region off the coast of WA where seas “were quite heavy with halibut” and whales could be found. During several research cruises over the last several years, we found that what the Makah called the Big Prairie, also named the Juan de Fuca eddy, was indeed a productive region and an initiation site for *Pseudo-nitzschia* HABs that impact crabbing and clamming. By *sharing this knowledge*, an early warning system for these HAB was co-designed with Indigenous scientists to promote seafood safety for all coastal people. This knowledge and our research together have led to the development of the Pacific Northwest HAB Bulletin, a synthesis of data from ORHAB monitoring, weather reports, models, and more, known to be important in forecasting HABs. This early warning Bulletin, provided to State and tribal co-managers of razor clams during harvesting season, enabled them to respond quickly to impending HABs by permitting selective harvest at safe locations or enabling pre-emptive increases in harvest limits when

HABs are lurking offshore. The Bulletin allowed for safe harvest only through a collaborative effort made possible through *mutual respect* that has been cultivated over many years. Matt Hunter, an Oregon State shellfish manager, commented that the Pacific Northwest (PNW) HAB Bulletin allowed a safe, pre-emptive increase in the clam harvest limit after months of closures due to domoic-acid in clams. He stated, “*The Long Beach, Washington razor clam opening and increased bag limit was a boon for Oregon north coast economies as well. A lot of people were hungry for clams*”.

Science advancement through collaboration

The establishment of mutual respect has allowed our scientific goals to be expanded into areas that we could only dream about two decades ago when our joint work began. With the Makah, Quileute, Quinault tribes and other partners, joint funding was received in 2020 for a project to deploy the Ocean Aero Triton, an autonomous unmanned submersible vehicle (AUSV), to sample HAB organisms and toxins off the coast of Washington State. Because rough seas and bad weather often prevent sampling of these dynamic ocean regions using small boats, the AUSV is a safe and effective alternative to in-person sampling. The samples collected by the Triton will be analyzed at tribal labs and used to improve the forecast provided by the PNW HAB Bulletin. Seawater samples from HAB “hotspots” or initiation sites provide an early warning of toxins that can affect coastal shellfish (crabs and clams) harvest.

Fig. 2. The Triton AUSV off the coast of Washington State. Credit: Bill Burns/Ocean Aero.

Conclusions

To summarize the Sato-umi approach: 1) humans are a part of nature; 2) community-driven science is the longest lasting approach to collaborative projects; 3) coastal residents need to be an integral part of our science. Our relationship with nature is not just a sense of “being close to nature to heal ourselves” but includes a reverence for nature to address issues such as the increasing intensity and changing global distribution of HABs. This closeness to nature is achieved by working with community members to conduct our joint scientific inquiries – by being inclusive from the inception of a scientific idea. As the Indigenous scholar Robin Kimmerer says “the relationship between the self and the world is reciprocal. It is not a question of first getting enlightened or saved and then acting. As we work to heal the earth, the earth heals us (Kimmerer, 2015).”

Whether fishing together, collecting clams from a windy beach, or conducting collaborative science, each person’s attention to protective, sustained engagement with nature can create a ripple effect for

conservation and build communities with a sense of solidarity, sharing, and a collective mission to care for each other and the planet. Ocean researchers, lawmakers, industries, managers of natural resources, and the general public committed to envisioning “the science we need for the ocean we want” are coming together during the 2021-2030 [UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development](#) to design ocean solutions to combat climate change, environmental degradation, and societal problems like HABs. This initiative stems from the paradigm that both oceans and people will benefit from conservation practices and advocacy for balanced approaches to science and solutions that serve society. Indeed, oceans and humans are undeniably linked: our approach to resource use on land, sea, and in the air affect ocean health and in turn the health of the oceans influences us (e.g., Fleming *et al.*, 2019; Franke *et al.*, 2020).

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